

LEPTOPHIS DEPRESSIROSTRIS (Satiny Parrot Snake): REPRODUCTION. *Leptophis depressirostris* is a slender green vine snake found from the Eastern slopes of Nicaragua to the Northern tip of Ecuador (Savage, 2002). On 29th November 2002 an adult female of this species (total length 780 mm; tail 213 mm; 66.2 g) was found during an expedition to the Tortuguero area of Costa Rica. The specimen was captured for identification during a visual survey of coastal forest inside the Parque Nacional Tortuguero. It was removed from a *Manicaria* swamp habitat (Myers, 1990) and taken back to our field base, the Cano Palma Biological Station, for more detailed observation. *Leptophis depressirostris* is an infrequently seen species identified by having a distinct loreal scale and two heavily keeled paravertebral scale rows on the dorsum (Savage, 2002). On closer inspection the individual appeared to be gravid and was provided with a wet, moist area within a vivarium. The snake was kept for two days before it deposited a clutch of five eggs, and then released a few days later. Its post-oviposition weight was 47.2 mm. After hatching the four neonate specimens were measured (length and mass) and then measured again after seven days before their release (near site of the captured parent). Measurements and hatching data for these individuals are presented in Table 1.

Information on reproduction in *Leptophis depressirostris* appears to be meagre, the only published record of which I am aware being that of Dundee & Liner (1974), who collected three eggs together with four old eggshells in a bromeliad 3.5 m high on an Atlantic slope. The eggs measured 35–48 mm, and the hatchlings were 186–198 mm.

Measurements presented here show that hatchling size in *L. depressirostris* is variable, although whether hatchling size is related to egg or adult female size is questionable and must await the availability of further data. It is interesting to note, however, that the

relative aseasonality of the Tortuguero area (receiving its heaviest rains and annual maximum of 6000 mm from November – February) may have a direct affect on hatchling emergence, and possibly also mating times of *Leptophis* spp. in the area.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I thank The Canadian Organization for Tropical Education and Rainforest Conservation (COTERC) for permission to study at Cano Palma Biological station, Richard Orton, and I also acknowledge The Ministerio de Recursos Naturales Energia y Minas and Farnborough College of Science and Technology for licences and help.

REFERENCES

- Dundee, H. A. & Liner, E. A. (1974). Eggs and hatchlings of the tree snake *Leptophis depressirostris* (Cope). *Brenesia* 3, 11–13.
- Myers, R. L. (1990). Palm swamps. In *Ecosystems of the World 15: Forested Wetlands*. Ch.11, pp. 267–278. Lugo, A. E, M. Brinson & S. Brown. (Eds). Oxford: Elsevier.
- Savage, J. M. (2002). *The Amphibians and Reptiles of Costa Rica: a Herpetofauna between two Continents, between two Seas*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.

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Table 1. Egg measurements and hatchling data.

Egg	Wt(g)	EGGS		HATCHLINGS		
		Size (mm)	Hatch	TOTAL (mm)	>7 days (mm)	Wt(g)
1	3.6	30 x 14	11.30 25/02/03	287	308	2.6
2	3.7	28 x 14	14.40 26/2/03	284	302	2.6
3	3.6	27 x 14	12.25 27/02/03	262	275	2.5
4	3.5	28 x 14	15.30 27/02/03	280	297	2.6
5	3.6	31 x 14.5		NO HATCH		